

UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL FLUMINENSE
Instituto de Ciências Humanas e Filosofia
Departamento de Ciência Política
Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciência Política

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A SAQUAREMENSE IN NEWSPAPER
CLIPPINGS:

Oliveira Vianna writer

Supervisor: Professor Claudio de Farias Augusto

Niterói, RJ/Brazil
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A SAQUAREMENSE IN NEWSPAPER CLIPPINGS:

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Master of Arts in Political Science** in the Postgraduate Program in Political Science at the Fluminense Federal University

By

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ABSTRACT

This study critically examined one hundred and ten articles authored by Francisco José de Oliveira Vianna (1883-1951), published in newspapers to reconstruct his thinking as a columnist. These texts are part of the collection of Casa Oliveira Vianna, Niterói/RJ, catalogued as "newspaper clippings". These articles were printed in daily newspapers, magazines and booklets. We were motivated to do the research based on the following questions: (i) Which Oliveira Vianna persona will we find in those newspaper articles? (ii) Would there be a correlation between the themes presented in his books and his articles? (iii) What would be the recurrent themes in these articles? (iv) When did the themes appear? (v) When were they more frequent? These questions appear to be less explored in the literature of the Social Sciences. It is in this gap that we insert the present work.

Keywords: Collective Action; Corporatism; Liberalism; Democracy.

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